

Effect of P application on agronomic characters, yield and yield components of lowland transplanted rice in acid-sulfate soils. Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam, 1983 wet season.

Method of P application	Rate (kg P/ha)	Seedling mortality (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% heading	Lodging (1-9 scale)	Panicles/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle	Unfilled grains (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Response to P (kg grain/kg P applied)
Control	0	39.6	95	107	1	4.2	17.5	1.43	30.5	33.6	31.6	0.96	
Full as basal	17.5	1.7	120	96	5	9.0	19.9	2.38	57.8	32.4	27.2	4.26	188.5
1/2 basal + 1/2 at 15 DT	17.5	1.8	120	97	3	8.9	20.0	2.16	54.3	38.5	28.5	3.92	169.1
1/2 at 15 DT + 1/2 at 30 DT	17.5	16.7	105	103	1	6.7	18.8	1.93	51.8	29.1	27.0	2.31	77.1
Full at 15 DT	17.5	11.1	109	102	1	7.2	19.0	1.80	46.5	33.4	28.3	2.85	108.0
Seedling root dipped in P slurry	17.5	3.1	115	100	3	9.6	18.9	1.90	51.7	35.2	28.1	4.12	180.5
Full as basal	26.2	1.2	125	96	5	9.2	19.5	2.08	53.3	34.5	27.9	4.11	180.0
CD (0.05)						1.6	1.2	0.20	11.3	5.6	2.6	0.55	
CV (%)						14.2	4.2	7.0	15.3	11.1	6.1	11.5	

low pH at planting and acute P deficiency are the major problems on these soils.

We conducted a field trial in the 1983 wet season to evaluate the effect on stand establishment and yield of methods of applying P. Seven treatments were tested in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil was clayey with 0.232% total N, 0.027% total P, 0.52% SO₄²⁻, 1.111 meq Al³⁺/100 g soil, and pH 3.7 at transplanting.

On 27 Jul 1983, we transplanted 38-d-old E425 seedlings spaced 20 × 15 cm. All plots received 80 kg N/ha as urea (30 kg N/ha basal + 20 kg N/ha 15 d after transplanting [DT] + 30 kg N/ha at 40 DT) and 20.5 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. P was applied as superphosphate (9% P).

A phosphate slurry was prepared by mixing superphosphate with soil and water in the ratio 1:1.5:2.5. Seedlings were dipped in slurry for 12 h before transplanting. About two-thirds of the slurry was consumed in treatment; the leftover was uniformly applied to the relevant plots to maintain a P level of 17.5 kg/ha.

In basal and split application, superphosphate was broadcast on the soil surface.

Missing hills were counted at panicle initiation. Lodging was scored on a 1-9 scale at maturity. The crop was harvested between 26 Oct and 8 Nov, depending on crop maturity in the different treatments.

Basal application, irrespective of quantity applied, resulted in lower seedling mortality (see table). It also appears to have augmented root development, increasing nutrient absorption.

Symptoms of P deficiency — narrow, short, and erect leaves with dirty dark green color and stunted plants with limited tillers — were high in control. Basal P enhanced tiller production and plant height and hastened crop maturity. That crop lodged moderately because of increased height and heavier panicles, but lodging did not affect grain yield.

At 17.5 kg P/ha, basal P resulted in significantly higher grain yield than other P application methods except seedling root dipped in phosphate slurry and split-applied P (1/2 basal + 1/2 at 15 DT). Basal application increased the yield mainly through increased number of panicles (higher survival of seedlings and more effective tillers/hill) and filled grains/panicle. Higher 1,000-grain weight in the absence of P might be attributed to reduced competition among fewer spikelets in the panicle.

Basal application of 17.5 kg P/ha resulted in maximum P efficiency. □

Effect of sulfur source and fertilizer on rice yield

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We studied the effect of S source and fertilizer on yield, verified earlier finding on applying 100 kg N/ha as urea with 1/2 t gypsum/ha, examined the effect of adding gypsum with the common farmer practice of 17:17:17 mixture and DAP, and separated the effects of Ca and S.

A 1980-81 kharif field trial involved 14 treatments in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Plot size was 24 m². Soil was sandy clay loam, pH 7.6, low soluble salts, EC 0.4 mmho/cm, with 273 kg N/ha, 7.32 kg P/ha, 292 kg

Grain and straw yields with different S fertilizers. Madurai, India, 1980-81 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)
Control	4.0	5.9
U 100 kg N/ha + CaO 27 kg/ha (20 kg Ca/ha)	4.3	6.6
AS 100 kg/ha alone	5.1	7.3
U 100 kg N/ha + elemental S 30 kg/ha	5.2	9.9
U 100 kg N/ha + elemental S 60 kg/ha	4.8	9.4
U 100 kg N/ha + G 250 kg/ha	5.4	10.9
U 100 kg N/ha + G 500 kg/ha	6.1	12.3
CaO 27 kg/ha alone (20 kg Ca/ha)	3.6	5.8
DAP 22 kg P/ha alone	4.0	6.9
TSP 22 kg P/ha alone	3.5	7.2
G 500 kg/ha alone	3.7	5.6
17:17:17 mixture	3.8	6.9
DAP + G 500 kg/ha	5.4	7.4
17:17:17 mixture + G 500 kg/ha	5.1	6.1
CD	0.4	0.3

^a U = urea, AS = ammonium sulfate, DAP = diammonium phosphate, G = gypsum, TSP = triple superphosphate.

K/ha, and 18 kg S/ha.

Urea to 100 kg N/ha was added with the 17:17:17 mixture and with DAP. Muriate of potash at 42 kg K/ha was applied for all treatments. Gypsum,

elemental S, and calcium oxide were applied basally.

Urea at 100 kg N/ha plus gypsum at 1/2 t/ha overwhelmingly increased yield (see table). Gypsum at 1/2 t/ha with

17:17:17 mixture and DAP equaled urea at 100 kg N/ha plus gypsum at 1/4 t/ha. S enhanced yield more than Ca. Gypsum is an easily available and cheaper source of S than elemental S. □

Efficiency of phosphorus form combined with organic manure in rice - rice cropping

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We compared direct and residual effects of phosphate rock and superphosphate on IR20 in 1982-83 kharif (wet season) and rabi (dry season). Treatments were imposed on the kharif crop, residual effects were studied on the rabi crop in a randomized block design replicated three times.

Both crops received 100 kg N and 42 kg K/ha. Soil was clay loam, with 220 kg available N/ha, 4.3 kg P/ha, 271 kg available K/ha, and pH 8.0. Organic manures were farmyard manure

Grain yield and return of phosphate and organic manure combinations. Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Return ^a / \$ invested
	Kharif	Rabi	
Farmyard manure alone	4.7	4.7	1.87
Farmyard manure + superphosphate	5.4	5.0	2.06
Farmyard manure + rock phosphate	4.9	5.4	2.10
Compost alone	4.7	4.8	1.98
Compost + superphosphate	5.6	4.6	2.03
Compost + rock phosphate	5.2	5.0	2.12
Greenleaf manure alone	5.9	4.8	1.93
Green leaf + superphosphate	5.9	4.9	2.09
Green leaf + rock phosphate	5.0	5.3	2.03
Superphosphate alone	5.4	4.9	2.10
Rock phosphate alone	4.4	4.9	1.90
Control (no Organic manure)	4.0	4.0	1.54
CD (0.05)	0.1	0.5	

^a Av of 2 seasons.

(FYM) — 0.05% N, 0.11% P, 0.42% K; composted water hyacinth — 1.5% N, 0.34% P, 1.25% K; and leucaena green leaf manure — 3.0% N, 1.7% P, 2.08% K.

The efficiency of superphosphate and rock phosphate improved when they were combined with organic manures (see table). Superphosphate applied with organic manure had highest direct effect. Superphosphate with leucaena green leaf

manure was best. Rock phosphate efficiency improved with composted water hyacinth.

Residual effects of all organic manures and P were equal. Rock phosphate with organic manure was better in obtaining high grain yield. FYM was the best in improving rock phosphate efficiency. Composted water hyacinth with rock phosphate gave the highest net return. □

Effect of Azospirillum on ASD16 rice

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We evaluated the effect of *Azospirillum* on grain yield of ASD16 (110 d duration) Jun-Oct 1986. Five N levels (0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha) and 4

Azospirillum treatments (control, seed treatment, seedling dip, and field application) were examined in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Available NPK was 298-75-164 kg/ha.

Yield differences due to *Azospirillum* treatment as well as the interaction between *Azospirillum* and N levels were not significant. All four N treatments were significantly superior to the control. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Rice-based fish and vegetable cropping system in coastal saline soils

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In the coastal saline soils of the Sundarbans, rice is grown only during the monsoon season. No crop is grown during the winter and summer seasons because good quality irrigation water is lacking and soil salinity is high. Saline water is plentiful throughout the year.

Yield and income with different rice - fish - vegetable cropping systems in Barrackpore, India, 1982-85.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Rice	3.4	398.00	150.00
Rice + freshwater fish	3.4	855.30	395.30
Rice - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	3.4	1297.60	624.60
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	3.4	1754.90	869.90
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	3.4	2594.30	1294.30
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	10.7		